

ADVANTAGES OF THE PROGRAM ICSI IN ASSISTANT REPRODUCTIVE TECHNOLOGIES (ART)

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Annotation: ART – assisted reproductive technology, is by far the most accurate and productive technology for preventing infertility in modern medicine. ART covers several programs, such as: In vitro fertilization (IVF), intracytoplasmic sperm injection into the oocyte (ICSI), intracytoplasmic sperm injection based on morphological characteristics (IMSI), IUI (insemination), testicular biopsy (TESE), etc. In this article we will talk about the advantages of ICSI over other programs.

Key words: ICSI, micromanipulator, sperm pathology, holding, oocyte, Kruger table, immobilization.

ICSI (intracytoplasmic sperm injection) is a rather complex procedure in the embryology laboratory with a complex technology mechanism, since this procedure requires not only precision, but also the dexterity and skill of the embryologist.

As mentioned above, the ICSI procedure has a complex mechanism for a complete presentation and this article describes it step by step:

At the initial stage, the couple undergoes a comprehensive examination. If abnormalities are detected that can be eliminated, it is necessary to undergo a course of treatment and recovery.

Before undergoing the procedure, patients need to donate blood for a number of tests:

- general clinical and biochemical analysis;
- determination of Rh factor and blood group;
- detection of sexually transmitted and infectious diseases;
- checking coagulability and hormone levels.

In addition, a general urine test is done. Men additionally donate semen for a spermogram, women - a smear to exclude hidden infections.

How is the ICSI procedure performed?

The use of ICSI as an assisted reproductive technology includes several stages.

First stage. First, the ovaries are stimulated. To do this, the woman takes hormonal drugs and then special medications. Hormones are administered over 1–2 weeks according to an individual regimen. When with their help the desired state of the body is achieved, hyperstimulation agents are prescribed. The course of taking them is also about 2 weeks.

The result of the first stage is an increase in the number of follicles. Throughout the course of taking medications, monitoring is carried out using ultrasound and blood tests.

Second phase. This is the stage of preparation for fertilization, and it begins with the collection of partners' biomaterial. Oocytes are obtained from mature follicles, which are removed by puncture. After the eggs are collected, the endometrium begins to prepare for implantation of the embryo, and the woman is prescribed another course of hormones.

In parallel with the puncture, seminal fluid is collected from the partner. The choice of method depends on the characteristics of the male reproductive system. The sperm are then separated and prepared for fertilization. There are also several variants of techniques that are used depending on how viable the sperm are.

Third stage. At the third stage, artificial insemination occurs. To do this, the laboratory technician takes a mature egg and the most suitable sperm. The selected viable sperm is injected with a thin injection needle under the oocyte membrane. The operation is carried out manually. The fertilized egg is placed in a nutrient medium for several days. When the embryo matures, it is transplanted into the uterine cavity.

Fourth stage. After preparation, collection of biological material and fertilization of the egg using the ICSI method, the mature embryo is transferred to the uterus. The outcome will be considered successful if the embryo takes root and begins to develop. To help the female body in this case, progesterone is prescribed.

IVF and ICSI methods differ from each other only in the way the egg is fertilized. In the first case, everything happens naturally; in the second, the sperm enters the oocyte with the help of an embryologist. Otherwise, both of these procedures are the same, so it is impossible to clearly determine which one is better. We can only say for sure that ICSI is a more expensive operation. Therefore, infertile couples first undergo classical IVF and only after no results are recommended to use ICSI technology.

Intracytoplasmic sperm injection, i.e. the introduction of a sperm into an egg with a syringe. The couple undergoes a medical examination: the woman has an ultrasound of the uterine cavity, endometrium and fallopian tubes, biochemical blood tests, etc., the man has a spermogram according to the Kruger criteria (Table 1) and biochemical blood tests.

Kruger criteria		
Criteria:	Patient:	Normal:
Volume:		1-2.5 ml
Liquefaction time:		20 min
Total sperm count:		1-46 mln
		35%
Total number of motile sperm (%):		35%
Sperm morphology(%):		7%
Agglutination:		

After passing the med. After examination, the fertility specialist begins stimulation of the woman’s ovaries. After 8 days of stimulation, transvaginal puncture of oocytes from the ovary begins. The embryologist captures the oocytes using a stereo microscope and places them in a washing solution to clear the oocyte of cumulus (liquid with the oocyte inside). After clearing the oocyte of cumulus, the embryologist places the oocyte in a culture medium. The medium provides nutrition for the egg, then after 2-4 hours the ICSI program begins.

The embryologist prepares a micromanipulator for sperm injection, places injection syringes in the manipulator, etc. In modern medicine, a micromanipulator is the most effective procedure because with it you can accurately and safely insert a sperm into an egg, even a sperm with low activity and immobile, and this is the whole advantage of this method. An experienced embryologist is required to control the laser micromanipulator, since the procedure requires precision and subtlety. In this method, morphologically normal sperm play an important role, since the selection and immobilization of the sperm occurs manually.

The manipulator has 2 needles inside which there are cavities: injection and holding (holder). As shown in, the injection needle sucks the sperm from the

cup with the medium and introduces it into the finished egg; The holding needle serves as a holder for the egg, inside which there is a vacuum to make it easier for the sperm to implant. All needles, cups, etc. are disposable and reuse is strictly prohibited. The micromanipulator has an anti-vibration table to prevent vibration during manipulation. The slightest friction has a huge impact on the manipulator.

After completing the ICSI procedure, the embryologist places the fertilized egg in a plate incubator, thereby observing the growth of the blastomere. On the second day, the embryologist assesses the presence of blastomeres and DNA fragmentation of the zygote. On the fifth day, the embryologist checks the embryo for the presence of “hatching” (hatching of the oocyte from the zone pellucida); if the oocyte fails to hatch on its own, the embryologist will begin the assisted hatching procedure. In this procedure, the embryologist cuts the embryo capsule using a micromanipulator syringe, thereby helping to remove the embryo from the capsule. On the sixth day, the embryologist evaluates the condition and quality of the embryo, then the finished embryo is transplanted into the endometrium of the uterus.

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